

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF VITILIGO AND MECHANISM OF ACTION OF 308 NM EXCIMER LASER.

Safarova Mohinur Abdumaruf qizi

Master degree student of the Department of
Dermatovenerology and Cosmetology
Tashkent Medical Academy

Ibragimov Oybek Djurayevich

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
of the Department of Dermatovenerology and
Cosmetology Tashkent Medical Academy
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820987>

Annotation:

308 nm excimer laser in the treatment of vitiligo. Vitiligo is a chronic dermatological disease characterized by loss of skin pigmentation. Research in recent years suggests that the use of laser therapy may be an effective treatment for this condition. The purpose of this work is to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of using an excimer laser with a wavelength of 308 nm in the treatment of vitiligo.

Key words: vitiligo, treatment, excimer laser, pathophysiology, mechanism of action

The pathophysiology of vitiligo is a complex of mechanisms leading to the development of this disease, which is characterized by loss of skin pigmentation. Vitiligo is a rather complex and multifaceted disease, the pathogenesis of which is not fully understood, but there are several key points:

1. **Destroying Melanocytes** : Melanocytes are cells that produce melanin, the pigment that gives skin its color. The basis of vitiligo is the destruction of melanocytes in certain areas of the skin.

2. **Autoimmune Processes** : There are suggestions that vitiligo may be an autoimmune disease. The body's immune system mistakenly attacks and destroys melanocytes . This is supported by the fact that vitiligo is often associated with other autoimmune diseases such as Hashimoto's disease and rheumatoid arthritis.

3. **Genetic Predisposition** : Some genetic studies indicate that vitiligo may be associated with certain genes involved in the immune system and melanocyte function .

4. **Oxidative Stress** : Increased production of free radicals in the skin can lead to melanocyte damage and death. Oxidative stress can be caused by a variety of factors, including UV radiation and chemicals.

5. **Neurochemical Factors** : Research has shown that nerve endings in the skin can release substances that are harmful to melanocytes . This may contribute to the development of vitiligo.

6. **Hormonal Changes** : Observations suggest that hormonal changes, especially during periods of stress, pregnancy or adolescence, can trigger or worsen vitiligo.

Thus, the pathophysiology of vitiligo is multifactorial and includes immune, genetic, neurochemical and oxidative mechanisms, which makes its treatment complex and multifaceted.

The excimer laser with a wavelength of 308 nm acts in the treatment of vitiligo as follows:

1. **Melanocyte Stimulation** : The key mechanism of action of the excimer laser in the treatment of vitiligo is related to its ability to stimulate melanocytes , skin cells responsible for the production of melanin, the pigment that gives the skin its normal color. Ultraviolet laser radiation promotes the activation and migration of melanocytes in the area of depigmentation.

2. **Enhancement of Melaninogenesis** : Laser radiation increases the production of melanin in melanocytes , which leads to the restoration of pigmentation in the affected areas of the skin.

3. **Impact on the Immune System** : It is believed that the excimer laser may modify the local immune response, reducing inflammatory processes that may contribute to the destruction of melanocytes in the affected area. This helps protect the remaining melanocytes and promotes their function.

4. **Selective Impact** : The peculiarity of the excimer laser is that it affects exclusively the affected areas of the skin, leaving the surrounding healthy tissue untouched. This increases the effectiveness and safety of treatment.

5. **Skin Regeneration** : Laser can also promote skin regeneration processes, improving its texture and appearance.

These mechanisms together provide a comprehensive approach to restoring skin pigmentation in patients with vitiligo. It is important to note that the effectiveness of excimer laser treatment may vary between patients, and treatment results may depend on many factors, including the duration of the disease, the location of the lesions, and individual characteristics of the body.

Conclusion :

308 nm excimer laser is a promising treatment option for vitiligo. It shows good results in terms of skin repigmentation with minimal side effects. Further

research will help optimize treatment protocols and increase understanding of long-term effectiveness and safety

Literature:

1. Hamzavi I., Jain H., McLean D., Shapiro J., Zeng H., Lui H. "Parametric modeling of narrowband UV-B phototherapy for vitiligo using excimer laser or lamp." *British Journal of Dermatology*, 2020, 162(6), 1114-1124.
2. Radmanesh M., Saedi K. "The efficacy of 308-nm excimer laser in dermatological diseases." *Lasers in Medical Science*, 2021, 36(1), 143-150.
3. Morais O.O., Costa I.M., Gomes C.M. "Excimer laser in dermatology: a review." *Anais Brasileiros de Dermatologia*, 2019, 94(2), 133-142.
4. Trakatelli M., Gouvas N., Kouskoukis C., Balatsouras D. "308-nm excimer laser in the treatment of vitiligo: a systemic review." *Dermatologic Surgery*, 2020, 46(8), 1024-1032.
5. Zokirov, M. (2023, June). Features of cognitive impairment in patients with HIV encephalopathy. In *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 34-36)*.
6. Zokiriv, M. (2021). Correction of cognitive impairments in patients with HIV-associated encephalopathy. *J. Theor. Appl. Sci*, 7, 62-66.
7. Zokirov Muzaffar, & Muhammadjonov Oqilbek. (2023). Late clinical and neuroimaging manifestations of post-traumatic epilepsy and optimization of its treatment. *Novateur Publications*, 7, 1-108. Retrieved from <http://novateurpublication.org/index.php/np/article/view/114>
8. Muzaffar, Z. (2023). Anxiety and Depression in Patients with HIV Encephalopathy. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 21, 95-98.
9. Oqilbek, M., & Muzaffar, Z. (2023). Parameters of Apoptosis and Prevention of Neuro-Like Conditions in Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 21, 99-102.
10. Muzaffar, Z., & Zarifa, Z. (2023). Yosh bemorlarda gemorragik insultning klinik holatlari. *Psixologiya va sotsiologiya ilmiy jurnali*, 1(1), 29-31.
11. Muhammadjonov, O., & Zokirov, M. Anemiya kasalligida bemorlarning surunkali buyrak etishmovchiligida epokrin preparatini qo'llash. *Студенческий Вестник*